

HYBRID FIBER COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Carl H. Zweben
Senior Research Engineer
E. I. du Pont de Nemours & Co., Inc.
Textile Fibers Department
Wilmington, Delaware
19898

Hybrids -- materials with two or more fibers in the same matrix -- greatly expand the range of properties that can be achieved with composites, such as fracture toughness and impact resistance; at the same time, they offer a way to reduce material costs.

In this paper we first survey aerospace and commercial applications involving hybrids of boron, graphite, glass and Kevlar® 49 aramid fibers. Typical aircraft applications involve fuselage, wing and tail structures, helicopter rotor blades, and jet engine fan blades. Commercial applications include sailboats, canoes, tennis rackets, golf club shafts, bows and arrows.

We present mechanical properties of unidirectional and fabric hybrid composites reinforced with "Thornel" 300 graphite and "Kevlar" 49 fibers. We find that the failure modes of hybrids are less catastrophic than those of graphite composites, offering greater structural reliability. Data for a hybrid made from "Kevlar" 49 fabric and AS-graphite tape indicate significant improvement in fracture toughness over the all-graphite control.

Cost projections are presented for hybrids in the forms of woven fabric -- use of which can substantially reduce fabrication costs -- and unidirectional tapes.

Introduction

Hybrid composites, which combine two or more different types of fibers in a common matrix, greatly expand the range of properties, such as fracture toughness and impact resistance, that can be achieved with composites. Furthermore, they can be significantly cheaper than materials reinforced with graphite or boron fibers alone. Applications and development programs involving hybrids have expanded rapidly in the past year, and annual funding in this area is in the millions of dollars.

There are many ways in which different fibers can be combined in a structure. They can be used in different layers or even in completely different parts of the same structural element. Fibers can also be blended together to form a hybrid tape or woven to form a hybrid fabric. The latter procedures result in what can be thought of as a new composite material having defined mechanical properties. From a design standpoint, the fact that the material is composed of different fibers can be ignored. The intimate blending of fibers can be likened to alloying in which metals are blended to obtain materials with properties and costs which cannot be obtained with individual constituents alone. For example, iron, aluminum and gold are most commonly used in alloy form. In this paper we will consider hybrid unidirectional tapes and woven fabrics as well as a laminate which combines fibers in discrete layers.

Table I shows typical properties of reinforcing fibers. Strengths are those which are commonly attained in composites. To obtain a meaningful comparison of costs, we present them on a volumetric as well as a weight basis. When one fiber is substituted for another, it is usually on an equal volume basis. For example, when a layer of one material is replaced by another of equal thickness, the volumes are the same but the weights can be very different. Therefore, when a quantity of fiber is replaced by an equal volume of cheaper, lower-density fiber, there is, in effect, a double savings.

Graphite and boron offer high stiffness and strength, but the impact resistance of composites made from them is relatively low. It has been shown that resistance to impact damage can be improved by the addition of fibers with high strains-to-failure such as E-glass, S-glass, "Kevlar" 29 and "Kevlar" 49 (Ref. 1-5). E-glass is the cheapest of the fibers in this group, but it also has a low stiffness and high density as does S-glass. "Kevlar" 29 also has a low stiffness, but its density is much lower than that of the glasses. Because of its relatively high stiffness and low density, "Kevlar" 49 is an attractive fiber for hybridization with graphite and boron. The major deficiency of "Kevlar" 49 composites is their relatively low compression yield and ultimate strengths. Reference 5 showed that these properties can be substantially improved by the addition of graphite fibers. Graphite and "Kevlar" 49 are

particularly well-suited for hybridization because their coefficients of thermal expansion are similar - slightly negative. This minimizes internal thermal stresses.

As mentioned above, lower material cost is a strong driving force for the use of hybrids. A recent development aimed at lowering fabrication costs has been the introduction of high-modulus-fiber woven reinforcement. The economies in use of fabrics has long been recognized in products reinforced with glass. Fabrics are not always efficient or economical for all applications, but they can expand the range of materials available to the designer, and are particularly useful for complex parts and surfaces with double curvature. We discuss properties of hybrid fabrics in a later section.

There are also hybrids in which high modulus fibers such as graphite and "Kevlar" 49 are used to improve the stiffness of glass fiber composites. Unidirectional "Kevlar" 49-glass hybrids are stiffer than glass and can have a higher compressive strength than "Kevlar" 49. However, the hybrid compressive yield is lower. "Kevlar" 49 is being used with glass in a number of applications where improved stiffness at a modest cost increment is required.

In this paper we survey some of the more significant of the many hybrid development programs and applications. We then present mechanical properties and cost data for "Kevlar" 49-"Thornel" 300 graphite/epoxy composites made from unidirectional tapes and woven fabrics. We also investigate the notch sensitivity of AS graphite-"Kevlar" 49 laminates.

Applications and Development Programs

As we mentioned in the Introduction, interest in hybrids has increased significantly in the past year, and funding of current programs runs into the millions of dollars. In this section we will survey some of the major aerospace and commercial programs and products.

Perhaps the most dramatic success with hybrids has been in the area of jet engine fan blades (Ref. 12). The inability of graphite and boron to successfully meet bird impact requirements has been the major obstacle to the acceptance of advanced composites for this application. However, it has been demonstrated recently that hybrid and all-"Kevlar" 49 blades can solve this problem. Figure 1 shows the QCSEE (Quiet, Clean, Short-haul Experimental Engine) under development by NASA Lewis Research Center for which hybrid blades and nacelle are under consideration. Figure 2 shows the QCSEE variable pitch fan.

Figure 3 shows a graphite/glass helicopter rotor blade developed by Sikorsky (Ref. 6). Despite the higher material cost, the lifetime cost is estimated to be significantly lower than that of aluminum because the composite has better fatigue performance.

As with metallic alloys, the choice of fibers depends on design requirements and structural configuration. For example, Henshaw and McElman (Ref. 7) performed a design study of a composite hat stiffener typical of a fuselage longeron. They concluded that the most effective configuration consists of unidirectional boron or graphite caps with "Kevlar" 49 fabric oriented at $+45^\circ$ for the web. A boron/"Kevlar" 49 hat stiffener (Fig. 4) failed in compression at 1200 lb. compared to 750 lb. for one of equal weight made from aluminum. This concept is currently being considered for application in high-performance aircraft.

Another example of hybrids applied to a high-performance aircraft is the box beam designed by Hadcock (Ref. 8) shown in Fig. 5. Based on a sophisticated trade-off study, boron/aluminum was used for the upper cover, a boron-graphite/epoxy hybrid for the lower, and graphite/epoxy for the substructure (beams and ribs). The covers were tested to failure, and exceeded design ultimate loads.

Helicopter fuselage skins are subjected to loads of lower intensity than those of fighter aircraft. A design study proposed by Rich, et al. (Ref. 9), proposed a hybrid shear panel of graphite tape with "Kevlar" 49 fabric to improve impact resistance. The improved impact resistance of the hybrids was verified experimentally in Ref. 4. Typical structural components incorporating "Kevlar" 49 and graphite hybrids for the CH-53 helicopter (Fig. 6) are being developed at Sikorsky under contract to NASA/Langley Research Center. The current production vehicle uses glass/epoxy in the cabin area because loads are relatively small and parts using this material are cheaper to produce than those of aluminum. It is hoped that similar economies and also weight savings can be realized in more heavily loaded structural components by use of hybrids. Figure 7 shows a typical structural detail.

Because graphite components tend to fail catastrophically, "Thornel" 300-"Kevlar" 49 hybrids are being considered for the critical main spar of the L-1011 in a development program funded by NASA/Langley Research Center (Ref. 10).

Among some of the other hybrid aerospace applications under development, we will just mention in passing: "Kevlar" 49-graphite helicopter rotor blades and drive shafts, and a boron-glass/epoxy overwing fairing for the F-14.

In addition to numerous aerospace hybrid applications, there are many commercial applications in production or under development which use hybrids. The "Dura-Fiber" golf club shaft (Fig. 8)

combines graphite fiber in tape form for axial stiffness with "Kevlar" 49 fabric for torsional stiffness and impact resistance.

Jennings uses "Kevlar" 49 to stiffen the tensile- and graphite the compressive surface of their wood compound bow (Fig. 9). The low stiffness-to-density ratios of the composites provide quick response when the bowstring is released and therefore impart greater energy to the arrow.

In addition to these commercial items, there are a number of other graphite-"Kevlar" 49 hybrids that are to be introduced shortly or are under development, including: tennis rackets, fishing rods, bicycle frames, javelins, skis and discus.

There have been a number of large sailboats in which "Kevlar" 49 was used to stiffen glass-reinforced hulls. One of these is the 66-ft. ocean racing yacht, "Phantom", manufactured by C & C Yachts (Fig. 10). Other glass-"Kevlar" 49 hybrids include racing canoes and kayaks which are significantly lighter and more impact resistant than their all-glass counterparts and have developed an impressive record of wins in international meets.

The shortage and increasing expense of good quality hardwood and excellent impact resistance and high stiffness-to-density ratio of "Kevlar" 49 has led to programs for "Kevlar" 49-wood and "Kevlar" 49-glass hybrid hockey sticks and paddles.

Preliminary results from programs to improve stiffness of pultruded glass shapes with "Kevlar" 49 have been good, and we anticipate that hybridization will expand the range of applications for this important class of structural elements.

In summary, recently there has developed a strong interest in hybrid composites which has led to the development of an impressive range of aerospace and commercial structural elements and products. We believe that these efforts will intensify in the future.

Properties of Unidirectional Hybrid Composites

In this section we present properties of "Kevlar" 49-"Thornel" 300 unidirectional hybrid composites made from prepreg tapes manufactured by Fiberite with their Type 934 epoxy resin. Ratios of graphite to-"Kevlar" 49 considered were 75/25 and 50/50. Properties of controls reinforced with the "parent" fibers only were also determined.

Table II presents for hybrids and controls tensile strength and modulus, short-beam shear strength, and compressive and flexure ultimate stress and stress at 0.02% offset, which is a measure of "yield". Specific gravities listed were determined by Fiberite. We believe that the true compressive strengths of the hybrids and

graphite are greater than those reported because these specimens, which were tested in a Celanese compression fixture, failed near the tabs. We plan to repeat these tests with re-designed tabs or use an alternate specimen such as sandwich beam. The nominal fiber volume fraction for all specimens was 0.60.

To assure a good distribution of both kinds of fibers in the hybrid specimens, flexure and tension specimens were 1-inch wide. Thicknesses were 20-ply (0.1 in.) and 7-ply (0.04 in.), respectively. Compression specimens cross-sectional dimensions were 0.26 in. x 0.12 in. Despite the fact that the uniformity of the fiber spacing in the hybrid prepreg tapes was poor, the scatter in measured properties was similar to that of the controls. Coefficients of variation varied between 1 and 9%; 5% was typical.

Table II also shows current prepreg costs based on a rule of thumb which says that prepreg cost per pound is about 20% greater than the per-pound cost of fiber from which it is made. This is lower than the overly-conservative 40% used in Ref. 5. We used current per-pound fiber price of \$50 for "Thornel" 300 and \$8.50 for "Kevlar" 49.

The data in Table II show that hybrids offer mechanical properties intermediate between those of the parent fiber controls at a significantly lower cost than graphite. These new composites give the designer a wider range of materials to choose from.

We observed that "Thornel" 300 tensile specimens shattered into hundreds of pieces upon failure, whereas the hybrids and "Kevlar" 49 did not. Figure 11 shows failed hybrid and control tensile specimens. In addition, hybrids and "Kevlar" 49 exhibit a definite "yield", or non-linearity, in compression. We believe that these failure characteristics are desirable properties from a reliability standpoint.

We plan to report in-plane shear, impact, fracture, and fatigue properties in a future paper.

Hybrid Fabric Composites

Fabric reinforcement offers economy of fabrication over unidirectional prepreg tapes and, in many cases, even over aluminum. Indeed, the bulk of continuous glass reinforcement is in fabric form. Aircraft fairings, boats, and many other structural items are made from glass-fabric reinforced resins. However, because of the low stiffness of glass, it has about reached the limit of application. "Kevlar" 49, because of its greater stiffness-to-density ratio, is more efficient than glass in many stiffness-governed or minimum gage applications, such as fairings. However, its low compressive strength is a significant limiting factor.

Hybrid fabrics overcome the limits of low compressive strength, offer higher stiffness-to-density ratios than either glass or "Kevlar" 49 alone and extend the range of applicability of fabric reinforcement to additional structural elements, such as control surfaces, fuselage skins, and aircraft flooring panels. In the area of sporting goods, potential applications include skis, tennis rackets, fishing rods, golf clubs, etc.

We are currently evaluating the properties of "balanced" fabrics - those having roughly equivalent properties in the warp (0°) and fill (90°) directions - woven and prepregged by Fiberite. Unidirectional fabrics, which have a high percentage of fibers in the axial direction - and therefore produce composites with properties approaching unidirectional tapes - will be considered in the future.

The fibers chosen were "Kevlar" 49 and "Thornel" 300. These materials have complementary properties and similar (negative) axial coefficients of thermal expansion, so that the problem of internal thermal stresses is not considered to be significant as it might be with glass and graphite. "Thornel" 300 is commonly available in 3000-filament yarns which have almost the same total cross-sectional area as "Kevlar" 49 1420 denier yarn (about $17 \times 10^{-5} \text{in}^2$), which facilitates weaving. We selected graphite/"Kevlar" 49 ratios of 75/25 and 50/50 in both warp and fill. Figure 12 shows a laminate made from a 50/50 fabric prepreg.

Table III shows the cost advantages of hybrids over graphite fabrics. A 50/50 blend is 40% cheaper than 100% graphite. The much greater cost of fabrics containing graphite compared to "Kevlar" 49 alone is caused by the difficulty in weaving graphite as well as its greater cost. With increasing experience, weaving costs are expected to drop.

We have just begun to evaluate the properties of the balanced hybrids and controls, but preliminary data are encouraging. Based on experience with graphite fabrics, we anticipate that it may be possible to obtain mean strengths which are 85-90% of those of [0/90] laminates made from unidirectional tapes, with lower scatter which would permit roughly equivalent design allowables.

Table IV shows warp tensile modulus and strength for composites made from hybrids and parent fiber controls. We note that the strength of the graphite control is 20% lower than that of the commercial fabric produced by Fiberite. We believe that the low strength results from use of low-strength yarn or damage to graphite yarns during weaving. Furthermore, void contents for hybrid and graphite laminates were high - 5 to 6%. We conclude that it should be possible to obtain significantly higher strengths for hybrids than those presented here by use of better finish on graphite yarns, along with better prepregging and laminate fabrication.

We plan to characterize completely the properties of these materials and [0/90] tape controls. Results will be presented in a future paper.

Fracture of Hybrid Composites

In Ref. 4 it was shown that the impact resistance of hybrid laminates consisting of 8 plies of AS-graphite with two layers of Style 120 "Kevlar" 49 cloth top and bottom had significantly better impact resistance than a thicker, all-graphite control. In this section we consider the notch sensitivity of these materials.

We tested 8- and 12-ply AS-graphite laminates made from 3M Co. prepreps which used their proprietary PR-286 epoxy resin. Laminates were symmetric about the middle surface, with alternate layers at 0° and 90°. These laminates would commonly be designated [(0/90)₂]_S and [(0/90)₃]_S, respectively. Hybrid laminates were made by adding to the top and bottom surfaces two plies of Style 120 "Kevlar" 49 fabric impregnated by Hexcel with their proprietary F-155 epoxy resin. Laminates were cured according to a procedure specified by 3M Co. for their PR-286 resin. Since this cure cycle differs from that recommended for the F-155 resin, hybrid laminate properties may not be optimum.

We used specimens with gage dimensions of 1 by 5 in. with a center notch nominally 1/4-in. long. The notch was initially cut to a length of 1/8-in. with a 1/32-in. end mil and then extended to the full length with a 9-mil jewelers saw. It was found in Ref. 11 that the relative notch sensitivity of different materials measured by this specimen was similar to that obtained with wider ones.

Table V presents data for notched coupons and unnotched controls. Each value is the average of three tests. There was little scatter - coefficients of variation were about 5%. The table shows, in addition to modulus for unnotched specimens, gross stress σ_g (load divided by overall cross-sectional area), net stress σ_n (load divided by net area at the notched cross-section), fracture toughness and stress concentration factor. Fracture toughness is defined as $K_C = \sigma_g (\pi a)^{-1/2}$, where a is the notch half length. We define the stress concentration factor K as (net or gross) failure stress of the unnotched controls divided by net stress of the notched coupons, σ_n . K measures the notch sensitivity of the material. If the only effect of the notch is to remove material, then σ_n is the same as the failure strength of the control, and $K = \text{unity}$. When $K > 1$, the notch causes a stress concentration, and the net failure stress is less than that of the control.

We note that the 8- and 12-ply graphite data are very close, and the slightly higher strength and modulus of the thicker laminate are probably the result of a higher volume fraction. The "Kevlar" 49 fabric has a slightly lower tensile strength than the graphite,

but its fracture toughness is about 70% greater. The associated stress concentration factor, 2.13, is significantly lower than that of graphite, 3.82. This is consistent with the observed higher fracture toughness. The greater notch sensitivity of AS-graphite/epoxy observed here in [0/90] laminates is similar to that for [0/90/+45] (quasi-isotropic) composites reported in Ref. 11.

The hybrid material has a modulus which is intermediate between those of graphite and "Kevlar" 49. The unnotched tensile strength is lower than either of the parent materials because the failure of the hybrid is precipitated by fracture of the graphite whose ultimate strain level is about 1%, whereas the "Kevlar" 49 fabric has an ultimate strain of 1.8%. We note that the hybrid ultimate strain level at 1.05%, is slightly higher than that of the graphite alone. Figures 13, 14 and 15 show typical failed fracture specimens.

The hybrid has a fracture toughness of $12.75 \text{ ksi-in}^{1/2}$, which is 32% greater than that of 12-ply graphite. The stress concentration factor, 2.46 is significantly lower than that of graphite. As in the case of modulus, the fracture resistance falls in between those of the parent materials.

Based on the improvements in fracture resistance observed in these limited tests of notch sensitivity, and previous studies which demonstrated improvements in impact resistance, we conclude that hybrids appear to offer significant advantages in reliability over all-graphite composites, and merit further consideration.

Summary and Conclusions

In this paper we have surveyed current applications and programs involving hybrid composite materials. Mechanical properties of unidirectional composites made from "Thornel" 300-"Kevlar" 49 prepreg tape were presented. Data show that hybrids are attractive engineering materials. Preliminary results from a program to define properties of materials reinforced with balanced-weave hybrid fabrics were reported and are encouraging. Cost data for hybrids show that these materials are substantially cheaper than graphite. Tests on [0/90] composites indicate that hybrids are less notch sensitive than graphite.

We plan further studies to define in-plane shear, impact and fatigue properties of laminates made from unidirectional tapes and balanced fabrics in addition to completing the mechanical property study on fabrics. We also plan to develop and characterize properties of composites reinforced with hybrid unidirectional fabrics.

We believe that the range of properties and cost reductions that can be obtained with hybrid materials - particularly those reinforced with fabrics - will greatly expand the use of advanced composites in the future.

Acknowledgment

We thank the Fiberite and Union Carbide Corporations for their cooperation in the hybrid fabrics development program and Mr. J. Fleetwood for his care and skill in testing.

References

1. Novak, R. C. and De Crescente, M. A., Composite Materials: Testing and Design (Second Conference) ASTM STP 497, American Society for Testing and Materials, 1972, pp. 311-323.
2. Chamis, C. C., Hanson, M. P., and Serafini, T. T., Composite Materials: Testing and Design (Second Conference) ASTM STP 497, American Society for Testing and Materials, 1972, pp. 324-349.
3. Moore, J. W., "PRD-49, A New Organic High Modulus Reinforcing Fiber", 27th Annual Meeting, Reinforced Plastics Div., Society of the Plastics Industry, Washington, D.C., February 1972.
4. Beaumont, P. W. R., Riewald, P. G., and Zweben, C., "Methods for Improving the Impact Resistance of Composite Materials", Foreign Object Impact Damage to Composites, ASTM STP 568, American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1975.
5. Riewald, P. G. and Zweben, C., "Kevlar® 49 Hybrid Composites for Commercial and Aerospace Applications", 30th Annual Conference of the SPI Reinforced Plastics/Composites Institute, Washington, D.C., February 1975.
6. Salkind, M. J., "The Twin Beam Composite Rotor Blade", Fibre Science and Technology, Vol. 8, No. 2, 1975, pp. 92-102.
7. Henshaw, J. and McElman, J., "Selective Reinforcement with Boron for Cost Effective Composite Structures", AIAA/ASME/SAE, 13th Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference, San Antonio, Texas, April 1972.
8. Hadcock, R. N., "The Application of Mixed Fiber Composites to Military Aircraft", 10th National State of the Art Symposium, Washington, D.C., Division of Industrial & Engineering Chemistry, American Chemical Society, June 1974.
9. Rich, M., et al., "Application of Composites to Helicopter Airframe and Landing Gear Structures", NASA CR-112333, National Aeronautics and Space Administration, Langley, Va., June 1973.

10. Fogg, L. D., "Hybrid Composite Design for Damage Tolerance", 2nd Conference on Fibrous Composites in Flight Vehicle Design, Dayton, Ohio, May 1974.
11. Zweben, C., "Fracture of Kevlar® 49, E-Glass and Graphite Composites", ASTM Symposium on Fracture Mechanics of Composites, Gaithersburg, Maryland, September 1974.
12. "Impact Resistance of Composite Fan Blades", NASA CR-134707, National Aeronautics and Space Administration, Lewis Research Center, Cleveland, Ohio, December 1974.

TABLE I
FIBER PROPERTIES

<u>Fiber</u>	<u>Modulus</u> (10 ⁶ psi)	<u>Tensile</u> <u>Strength</u> (ksi)	<u>Tensile</u> <u>Failure</u> <u>Strain</u> (%)	<u>Specific</u> <u>Gravity</u>	<u>Density</u> (lb/in ³)	<u>Cost</u>	
						<u>(\$/lb)</u>	<u>(\$/in³)</u>
Boron (4 mil)	60	460	0.77	2.60	0.094	250.00	24.00
Graphite ("Thornel" 300)	34	380	1.07	1.74	0.063	50.00	3.15
"Kevlar" 49	19	400	1.75	1.45	0.052	8.50	0.44
"Kevlar" 29	9	400	3.8	1.45	0.052	7.50	0.39
E-Glass	10.5	250	2.4	2.54	0.092	0.50	0.05
S-Glass	12.5	450	3.6	2.48	0.090	12.00	1.08

TABLE II

PROPERTIES OF UNIDIRECTIONAL "THORNEL" 300, "KEVLAR" 49
AND HYBRID COMPOSITES - NOMINAL FIBER VOLUME FRACTION = 0.60

Percentages of "Thornel" 300/ "Kevlar" 49 Fibers	Specific* Gravity	Tension		Compression		Flexure		Short Beam Shear Stress (ksi)	Prepreg Cost \$/lb
		Modulus (10 ⁶ psi)	Ultimate Stress (ksi)	Stress at 0.02% Offset (ksi)	Ultimate Stress (ksi)	Stress at 0.02% Offset (ksi)	Ultimate Stress (ksi)		
100/0	1.60	21.1	227	98.4	146	233	233	13.2	60
75/25	1.56	17.4	186	68.8	136	181	197	11.0	48
50/50	1.51	15.7	176	59.9	99.8	120	160	8.1	35
0/100	1.35	11.2	183	26.4	41.5	49.2	91.9	7.1	10

*Data supplied by Fiberite

TABLE III

PRICES FOR "THORNEL" 300-"KEVLAR" 49 HYBRID FABRICS

<u>Ratio of "Thornel" 300/"Kevlar" 49</u>	<u>Weight (oz/yd²)</u>	<u>Thickness (in.)</u>	<u>Price \$/yd²</u>
100/0	11.0	0.013	49.50*
75/25	10.2	0.0123	37.65*
50/50	9.7	0.012	29.13*
0/100	6.7	0.013	5.11

*Fiberite data - orders of 500-2500 linear yards

TABLE IV

TENSILE MODULUS AND STRENGTH DATA FOR BALANCED
FABRIC HYBRID COMPOSITES - WARP DIRECTION

<u>Ratio of "Thornel" 300/"Kevlar" 49</u>	<u>Modulus (10⁶ psi)</u>	<u>Strength (ksi)</u>
100/0	9.5	69.2
75/25	8.9	68.1
50/50	7.4	61.2
0/100	5.4	83.1

TABLE V

NOTCH SENSITIVITY OF [0/90] AS GRAPHITE-"KEVLAR" 49 HYBRID COMPOSITES

<u>Reinforcement</u>	<u>Modulus</u> (10 ⁶ psi)	<u>Thick.</u> (in.)	<u>Nominal</u> <u>Crack</u> <u>Length</u> (in.)	<u>Stress at</u> <u>Failure</u>		<u>Fracture</u> <u>Toughness</u> <u>K_c</u> (ksi-in ^{1/2})	<u>Stress</u> <u>Concentration</u> <u>Factor</u> <u>K</u>
				<u>Gross</u> <u>σ_g</u> (ksi)	<u>Net</u> <u>σ_n</u> (ksi)		
<u>AS Graphite (Tape)</u> 8-Ply	7.67	0.048	0	75.8	75.8	--	--
	--	0.048	0.25	14.88	19.88	9.37	3.82
12-Ply	7.87	0.072	0	78.5	78.5	--	--
	--	0.072	0.25	15.31	20.5	9.66	3.82
<u>"Kevlar" 49</u> (Style 120 Fabric)	4.17	0.030	0	72.9	72.9	--	--
	--	0.030	0.25	25.2	34.3	16.16	2.13
<u>Hybrid (8 Plies</u> <u>of Graphite Tape +</u> <u>4 Plies of "Kevlar"</u> <u>49 Fabric)</u>	6.32	0.078	0	66.5	66.5	--	--
	--	0.078	0.25	20.2	27.0	12.75	2.46

FIGURE 1 - QCSEE ENGINE (COURTESY R. W. KOENIG, NASA/LEWIS RESEARCH CENTER)

FIGURE 2 - QCSEE ENGINE VARIABLE-PITCH FAN (COURTESY R. W. KOENIG, NASA/LEWIS RESEARCH CENTER)

FIGURE 3 - H-53 HELICOPTER HYBRID ROTOR BLADE DESIGN (REPRODUCED FROM FIBRE SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, VOL. 8, NO. 2, pp. 92-102 BY PERMISSION OF THE PUBLISHERS, APPLIED SCIENCE PUBLISHERS LTD. - COURTESY DR. M. SALKIND, SIKORSKY AIRCRAFT)

FIGURE 4 - BORON-KEVLAR® 49 HYBRID STIFFENER

WING STRUCTURE - TEST COMPONENTS

FIGURE 5 - HYBRID WING BOX BEAM DESIGN (COURTESY R. N. HADCOCK, GRUMMAN AEROSPACE CORP.)

FIGURE 6 - CH-53 HELICOPTER (COURTESY DR. R. FOYE, NASA/LANGLEY RESEARCH CENTER)

FIGURE 7 - STRUCTURAL DETAIL FROM DESIGN FOR HYBRID COMPOSITE HELICOPTER FUSELAGE (COURTESY DR. R. FOYE, NASA/LANGLEY RESEARCH CENTER)

FIGURE 8 - "DURA-FIBER" GRAPHITE-KEVLAR® 49 GOLF CLUB SHAFT

FIGURE 9 - JENNINGS COMPOUND BOW USES KEVLAR® 49
AND GRAPHITE TO STIFFEN WOOD

FIGURE 10 - THE 66-FT. OCEAN RACING YACHT "PHANTOM"
MANUFACTURED BY C & C YACHTS

FIGURE 11 - FAILED UNIDIRECTIONAL TENSILE SPECIMENS

TOP TO BOTTOM:

- A. 50/50 "THORNEL" 300/KEVLAR® 49 HYBRID
- B. 75/25 "THORNEL" 300/KEVLAR® 49 HYBRID
- C. "THORNEL" 300 CONTROL
- D. KEVLAR® 49 CONTROL

FIGURE 12 - HYBRID LAMINATE MADE FROM 50/50 BLEND
"THORNEL" 300-KEVLAR® 49 EIGHT-HARNESS-SATIN FABRIC

FIGURE 13 - FAILED [0/90] AS-GRAPHITE/EPOXY FRACTURE SPECIMEN

FIGURE 14 - FAILED [0/90] KEVLAR® 49 STYLE 120 FABRIC EPOXY FRACTURE SPECIMEN

FIGURE 15 - FAILED [0/90] AS-GRAPHITE-KEVLAR® 49/ EPOXY HYBRID FRACTURE SPECIMEN